

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

ENHANCING WRITING SKILLS OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Annotatsiya. *Yozish-bu akademik muvaffaqiyat va kasbiy rivojlanishda muhim rol o'ynaydigan asosiy ko'nikmalardan biridir. Universitet talabalari uchun yozish o'z fikrlarini aniq va samarali ifodalash hamda rasmiy hujjatlarga oid muammolarni hal qilish va ushbu sohada yangi tushunchalarni o'zlashtirish uchun juda muhimdir. Yozish, shuningdek, savodxonlikning asosiy tarkibiy qismi bo'lib, u tanqidiy fikrlash, tahlil qilish va yangi g'oyalarni izlash jarayonini o'z ichiga oladi. Yaxshi paragraflar nafaqat o'quvchilarga matn mazmunini to'liq tushunish va ma'lum sohadagi bilimlarini oshirishga yordam beradi, balki yozuvchiga ham o'z fikrlarini tartibga solish, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va mantiqiy argumentlarni shakllantirishga undaydi. Yaxshi yozilgan maqola talabalarni o'zlariga nisbatan ishonchini oshirishga, mantiqiy yozishga, yuqori baholar olishga va muayyan sohalaridagi bilimlarini chuqur aks ettirishga yordam beradi. Yozish – bu yozuvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi aloqa turi bo'lib, u hamkorlik, ma'lumot almashish va o'zaro muloqotni ta'minlaydi. Shunday ekan, yozish, ayniqsa, oliy ta'limda tahsil olayotgan talabalar uchun juda muhim, chunki ular kelajakda davlat boshqaruvidagi turli sohalarining yetakchilariga aylanishadi. Ushbu maqolada universitet talabalari uchun yozish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga oid turli strategiyalar va yondashuvlar, shuningdek, ushbu sohadagi so'nggi tadqiqotlar va eng yaxshi amaliyotlar tahlil qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *qiyinchiliklar, o'quv jarayoni, tanqidiy fikrlash, texnologiya, vaqtni boshqarish, baholash, Sun'iy Intellekt (SI), hamkorlikda yozish.*

Аннотация. *Письмо — это один из основных навыков, который играет важную роль в академическом успехе и профессиональном развитии студентов. Для студентов университетов оно особенно важно, так как помогает ясно и эффективно выразить мысли, решать вопросы, связанные с официальными документами, а также осваивать новые концепции в данной сфере. Письмо также является фундаментальной составляющей грамотности, поскольку включает в себя критическое мышление, анализ и исследование различных вопросов с целью получения новых знаний. Грамотно составленные абзацы не только позволяют читателям полностью понять содержание и углубить свои знания в определенной области, но и помогают автору структурировать идеи, анализировать данные и логично выстраивать аргументы. Хорошо написанная работа способствует тому, что студенты становятся более уверенными, учатся логично излагать мысли, получают более высокие оценки и демонстрируют глубину своих знаний в различных сферах. Кроме того, письмо является формой общения между автором и читателем, обеспечивая взаимодействие, обмен информацией и сотрудничество. Таким образом, письмо играет важнейшую роль для студентов, особенно тех, кто получает высшее образование, поскольку в будущем они могут стать лидерами в различных государственных структурах. В данной статье рассматриваются различные стратегии и подходы к улучшению навыков*

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письма у студентов университетов, основанные на современных исследованиях и лучших практиках в этой области.

Ключевые слова: *трудности, образовательный процесс, критическое мышление, технологии, управление временем, оценивание, искусственный интеллект (ИИ), совместное написание текстов.*

Abstract. *Writing is one of the basic skills that plays a crucial role in academic success and professional development in students' life. For university students, writing is very important to express ideas effectively and clearly in order to solve some problems related to official documents and mastering new concepts in this sphere. Writing is also fundamental component of literacy which involves critical thinking, analyzing and researching something in order to find new insights. Good paragraphing not only allows readers to understand the content fully and sharpen knowledge in a certain sphere, but also encourage writer to organize ideas, analyzing data and building arguments logically. A well-written paper promotes students to become more confident and write more logically in order to get higher grades as well as to reflect depth of knowledge in some spheres. Writing is also a type of communication between writer and reader which allows them collaboration, transaction and interaction. Therefore, writing is crucial for students, especially who are studying in higher education as they will become future leaders in some branches of the government. This article explores various strategies and approaches to enhance the writing skills of university students, drawing on recent research and best practices in this area.*

Keywords: *challenges, educational process, critical thinking, technology, time management, assessment, Artificial Intelligence (AI), collaborative writing.*

Introduction. “How important is writing skill for university students?” If we focus more on this question, we have to pay more attention the way of writing skills of students in universities. Because we are living in technological era and we are using Artificial Intelligence (AI) on a daily basis and of course university students are also using it during lessons if they have to write or find something related to writing skills. As a result, students are becoming lazy, inactive using the advantage of Artificial Intelligence (AI) nowadays. Since Artificial Intelligence (AI) gives various information from other sources which had already been published online, students could be unaware from plagiarism which have huge negative impact on their writing or they become addict to Chatgpt, Google and so on. When it comes to question which was given above, writing skills allow us to acquire knowledge, practice different writing styles and improve critical and logical thinking of university students. If students do more research, they will gain more knowledge and skills which really help them during their life and workplace. Through writing essays, research papers and reports students often articulate their thoughts, ideas, opinions and realistic engagement to those contents and try to find new insights while writing. According to Kellogg (2008), writing is not only a means of communication but also

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a tool for learning, as it helps students organize their thoughts and deepen their understanding of the subject matter. In order to develop writing skills of university students, teachers should consider some challenges which students could face while writing essays, reports and tasks.

Main Challenges Faced by University Students

University students could come across variety of challenges in writing depending on their skill, level and experience in writing. Common challenges are:

- Lack of Clarity and Coherence:** University students often have difficulty structuring their arguments in a logic way to ensure their writing smoothly. As a result, their writing can be seen as a mass or unlogic.

- Grammatical range and accuracy:** there a lot of students who face challenges with using different grammar structures, punctuation, and spelling, which can have negative effect to overall quality of their writing.

- Realizing Academic Conventions:** there some disciplines and conventions in English which require specific writing styles and rules and students could struggle to adopt these styles. Some writing styles require direct or indirect message or tone which expose to think about audience.

- Time Management:** managing time while writing is also essential as it helps students to reduce stress and improve more focus on the content. Balancing different assignments and deadlines might lead to success in writing and maximize productivity.

Some useful strategies for Enhancing Writing Skills

In order to address these challenges which were given above, some beneficial strategies can be implemented to develop the writing skills of university students:

- Encouraging combination of regular reading and writing skills during the class.** Because many university students are becoming inactive especially reading and writing lessons as they easily use Artificial Intelligence (AI) in and out of the class, therefore their sub-skills such as logical and critical thinking skills are not developed enough. For the purpose of improvement in writing teachers could use combination of reading and writing skills in a lesson. Students are given a text and write a summary of the text in different style and students can learn to use new grammar structures which could be very helpful for their reports and essays. Contextual learning is one of the most effective ways of meaningful interaction in language learning [3]

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•**Enhancing vocabulary.** Students cannot write if they do not have enough vocabulary to write something. Teachers will help them to learn at least 15-30 words and collocations during the lessons and use them appropriately in their writing or make sentences for each vocabulary unit. If students have enough vocabulary their sentences may not be too repetitive or simple. They try to use collocations and advanced vocabulary in their writing which allows the reader to understand fully.

•**Writing Centers and Support Services:** Some universities have already established writing centers which provide students with access to writing tutors and resources. These centers can offer personalized feedback on writing assignments and help them to improve writing skills through one-on-one consultations and workshops [2]. In some countries it could be very difficult to organize such kind of services, some private universities, however, try to implement these services.

•**Collaborative Writing:** This type of writing involves two or more students work together to create, check and give feedback for a written document. With the help of this style, students will review their writing papers and get constructive feedback from their peers. This approach can not only help to revise weak areas for improvement, but also develop their logical and critical thinking. Collaborative writing provides students responsibility, division of tasks, effective use of technology and editing skills. It also affects quality of writing and speed reading as students are exposed to read quickly and think about how to write smoothly and effectively according to given text. [4]

•**Effective use of technology:** utilizing technology can also help to enhance students' writing skills. These days there are many writing tools such as Grammarly, Turnitin and Evernote which can provide feedback on grammar, organization, sentence structure coherence and cohesion for students' writing. Using these writing tools encourage students to write more and cohesively. By using these writing tools students can also analyze their mistakes in real time before submitting their work. [5]

•**Self-Assessment and Reflection:** university teachers can also encourage their students to engage in self-assessment as it will promote metacognitive awareness of their writing processes. By reflecting on their writing, students can realize their strengths and weaknesses, leading to targeted improvements and start working on weaknesses. Writing reflection for an article can also helpful for them as it exposes critical thinking. Recent studies show that self-assessment and peer-review helped

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Thai students to develop writing skills and those students were able to articulate their thoughts and ideas during writing classes. [1]

Conclusion

Despite many challenges in writing, students could learn effective use of Artificial Intelligence (AI), different writing tools and boost reading skills at the same time during writing classes. using vocabulary and collocations could motivate them to wrote smoothly and coherently. In addition to this implementing writing centers, promoting peer review, incorporating technology, and providing explicit instruction, universities can also create an environment that fosters strong writing skills. As students develop their writing abilities, they will be better equipped to succeed academically and professionally. As Batstone (1994) mentions that students can start using their productive skills if they have enough input which is a part of the learning process called intake. The more output could be produced by the process of sufficient input. [3]. Another author who worked on language learning process Schmidt (1990) explained that language learners pay conscious attention to the input and this kind of intake is known as noticing. [6]. In Uzbekistan nearly almost university students learn English as a foreign language (EFL) and they need noticing more than European students as Uzbek and English language are related to different families. Therefore, students should pay more attention their input and noticing since English has different grammar structures and alphabet.

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